

USE OF FILM IN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract

This study is based on the use of movies in language teaching for secondary level school education. In the line of language teaching, several experts have propounded the way of utilization of the existing new methods and techniques to improvise the language efficiency of both teachers and students. Nowadays, an audio-video display and explanation of the relevant context is widely used even in traditional classroom teaching methods. According to linguists and literature experts, the use of subject-matter related audio-video displaying is an effective and significant means as well as process of language teaching. It is found that there have been some studies between movies and students during effective education.

Therefore, the objective of the proposed study is to identify the effect of the harmonized relationship between the teacher, student, and movie in improving the listening, speaking, reading, and writing language skills. To achieve the goal of the objective of the proposed study, structured/unstructured questionnaires, key informant interview (KII), observation forms have been used to collect the information. The teachers, students and educational experts have been considered as the source of information. The information collected from the sources have been intensively discussed among the stakeholders and analytically described to derive the conclusion. Furthermore, qualitative methods have been applied to analyze the information and in drawing conclusions.

This study is based on the basic principles of exponents of experimental theory, including Frowell's demonstration method, Daisy Jan Marble's experimental demonstration method, and Palmer's direct method.

Keywords: Film, Language Teaching, Education

1. BACKGROUND

Movies are an effective medium of language communication. Language is the medium to reveal or demonstrate the cultural value, practice, and consciousness. The method of teaching by applying audio-video systems has been adopted since long before, however, its use in language teaching has been principally developed from the end of 20th century. Movies have been taken as a powerful tool/medium of language teaching after it was considered a new but effective extension of arts. Movies are also a formal sector which directly connects with several audiences. It is believed that the knowledge acquired from the audio-video used during teaching and learning remains long-lasting in comparison to the knowledge acquired from traditional teaching methods.

Movies play a significant role in developing language vocabulary, listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills. So, it can be said that there is an interrelationship between education and movies. As other categories

of literature (drama, story etc.), movies should also be included in the curriculum which can also play an important role in language teaching. 'Movie can explore any event in interesting ways that can be broadcasted, with a minimum cost and effort, in every corner of the country' (youtube.com). An informative movie can easily communicate/disseminate its language and contents in the society and develops the capacity of good listening, reading, understanding, speaking, and adaptation of the language.

Furthermore, the quotations of Raja Masum Rahi, 2001:27 and 2001:67 'Now the knowledge and education provided by cinema should be properly introduced in the universities and the film should be included in the university curriculum.' And 'Film is such an art form, which can survive only through language' can be taken as the foundation stone for the use of movie in modern education. Similarly, the statements 'There is a subject reference in the movie which is revealed to the audience by taking the basis and activities of living people or the natural world in the form of vivid pictures (Subedi, 2069:1, 'Language teaching is the teaching of skills and the content is secondary and linguistic skills are the main subject, but the film is such a subject, it is not the direct teaching of the content, but the development of linguistic skills in different ways (Sharma, 2074:1), 'Visual poetry is for the entertainment and education of the common people' (Bharat Muni), 'Films are scientifically considered visual poetry for theatrical purposes (Chaulagai, 2064:1) disseminate the meaningful background for the use of movie in language teaching.

Hence, film can be used as a medium to fulfill educational purposes, and film is an excellent medium to promote the development and expansion of language. In the background of using new methods and techniques for language teaching day by day, movies are also emerging as a major subject in the demonstrative teaching method. Subjects or aspects taught under performance teaching are - character acting, expression, language style, expression skills according to the character, dialogue etc. So, we can be confident that language teaching is effective and meaningful in the thematic centrality of movies

Therefore, the present study is useful from an academic point of view, in the context that the study research of this nature is very limited. The work of movies is to define the values and norms of the society and portray the reality of the society. Therefore, the present study has focused on how Nepali narrative films have reflected the educational aspects of Nepali society and how these films have influenced the education sector. The main topic of this research is to follow the study of film as an excellent medium for language teaching to develop, expand and enhance the language. The use of new methods and technologies for language teaching has been developed day by day. Under the new method used for language teaching, there is a film as a demonstration method.

2. RATIONALE

The use of movies in language teaching is an important topic for the present time. Through the medium of movies, students can achieve achievements such as various linguistic expression arts such as: oratory, using expressions according to dialogue characters, etc. Due to this, on the one hand, people will be able to give linguistic expression in a standardized form of Nepali language, on the other hand, it will help to develop and promote the cultural, religious, and linguistic identity of our country and broaden its importance.

Since there is no research on this subject so far, it will be useful to investigate: What is the status of the educational aspect of Nepali society by Nepali narrative movies? How is it used in teaching in schools? And so on.

3. OBJECTIVE

The prime objective of the proposed study is 'the use of movies in language teaching'. The study also reviews and elaborates on 'analyzing linguistic skills in the centrality of various linguistic expressive uses of Nepali movies.'

4. METHODOLOGY

The basic study method of the present research is to use integrated patterns among the sequential patterns of qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods. However, the title of the study suggests focusing more on qualitative analysis of subject matter. The details of applied methods are as below:

4.1 Literature Review

During the preliminary studies, the study has been speeded up based on some research papers and books published inside the country and some communication materials and books published from outside the

country. The reviewed literatures and publications are presented chronologically as follows:

Susan Hayward's (1996) work entitled "The Concept of Cinema Studies" is a dictionary of this film. It discusses the use of words used in films and how they are used, but it does not show how teaching is done through films.

Manu Bhandari (2004:200) in the book called 'Katha Pakatha', a story of a female character fighting against the injustice of the society is presented. It is trying to show that others want to be the same. Therefore, this book has been considered as suitable for this study.

Richard Ruston and Gerry Bettinson (2010:2) 'What is Film Theory' In this book it is mentioned about the development of film and its theory. In it, what are the benefits of studying film and how one can gain knowledge on many kinds of subjects by studying and teaching this subject in the university. Therefore, this book can be considered as an appropriate and important reference for this research.

Anand Mahesh, Ankur Raj Devendra (2008:7) focuses on Eastern and Western theatrical thought in 'Theory of Theatre'. The purpose of this collection of articles is for the person who studies it, colorists to become familiar with the basics and in what sense it is specific and can be analyzed by Western thinkers in an Indian sense. Therefore, this book is considered suitable for this research.

Saran Renu (2012) 'History of Indian Film' talks about the development of Hindi films and films made in different languages but did not find teaching related topics but it helps the research. Therefore, this research is considered appropriate.

Dhungel Madhav (2071) in 'Cultural Dominance in Nepali Films' studies films by touching on gender dominance. In the presented film, the linguistic variety used by the upper class, middle class and lower class is also shown. Although it is shown that the character should use language according to the theme and the language should be selected according to the class, it does not show how to teach language, but it teaches where and how the language has been used. So, this research of Dhungel is considered suitable for this study.

Giri Amar (2069: 217) in his book 'Culture' says that although he does not present a separate concept of language teaching, the film industry looks at the problems related to knowledge and skills.

While observing and reviewing the research questions based on the Nepali narrative film, Madhav Dhangel (2071) has studied the gender dominance of the film in his research paper entitled 'Cultural Dominance in Nepali Films'. While showing the gender hegemony in Nepali films, films like Prempinda, Dakshina, Bandhaki, Kaha Bhetiyela, Bato Muniko Phool, Notebook, Numafung, etc. have analyzed the gender situation found in these films based on the image and story presentation.

Film Development Board of the Government of Nepal (2071:3) National Movie Policy 2071, guiding principles state that "to play a role for the protection, promotion and development of all local languages, cultures and castes through movies". It also reveals a clear message that the teaching through movies is suitable for the development of language. But what is the priority of movies in language teaching? That is not shown in it.

International Journal of Education and Literacy Studies (2015), 'Movie Effectiveness on EFL Learner and Iraq School in Kuala Lumpur', spells out about the level of use and priority of movies in language teaching. It also acknowledges movies as a suitable tool for different multilinguals to learn and use the language. The 30-minute English DVD with subtitles displays Iraqi students learning the language. Therefore, this article is suitable for review of previous work.

Carolyn (year 2017) In 'Reading Film in the English Classroom', it is very fun to teach by showing a literary film through the demonstration method. While teaching, it is found that novels, plays, poems and other forms of literary films have their own importance and characteristics.

Rai Parashuram (2074: 40) in 'A Preliminary Study of Acting on the Movie Stage' says acting includes any language, religion, culture, values, beliefs, etc. According to his statement that acting is both audio and visual, movies help in language development through audio and visual, so even though this statement is not teaching, it can be considered as a suitable material for research.

Bhattarai Keshav (2076: 68) on 'Chalachitra Manch', films in the mother tongue are discussed to produce films with a linguistic majority and mother tongue films. It also seems suitable as Nepali language can be taught as the national language to different native speakers. Although the use of movies in language

teaching is not discussed here, this material seems appropriate for the research presented.

According to Neophys Mitesikas (2021) "For Tips for Learning Language Through Film and TV": Movies and TV is a good technology to solve your curiosity and curiosity to understand and speak other languages.

The reviewed literature clearly emphasizes that the use of movie (audio-video) is effective as well as impressive in language teaching and advocates for the inclusion of movie in university level education.

4.2. Sample Selection

For the present study, 5 movies out of 10 Nepali movies produced by Keshav Bhattarai have been selected using the purposive sampling method. The character acting, character-appropriate language-presentational, accentual character-appropriate language-communicative social, cultural environmental expressions of the 5 selected movies have been analyzed from the educational context. To make the study factually reliable and valid, 10 students, 1 professor and 1 educationist have been voluntarily selected from each of the 7 schools where class teaching is conducted through movies. Therefore, the materials that were interviewed and filled in the observation form with these mentioned personalities are the primary sources of this research. The results from these students, teachers and academics have been standardized with the research director, subject experts.

For the observation visit and interaction, Nandi Secondary School of Kathmandu, Nepal has been selected as the prime source of information.

4.3. Direct Observation

To collect information with direct observation, the presenter visited Nandi Secondary School, Kathmandu, Nepal. During the visit, it had been noticed that the teacher was showing a movie (Audio-video) relevant to the subject matter using you-tube channel. The teacher at the same school Ms. Prabha Pantha demonstrated the use of smart television to search for subject related audio-videos and movies. When asking Srijana Ghorasaini, a student at the same school, do you like teaching using only textbooks or do you like teaching by showing movies? His answer to this question was that while teaching from a book, the attention goes to the other end at that time, but when teaching through movies, the entire attention goes to the movie.

4.4. Key Informants Interview (KII)

Sita Poudel, a teacher who teaches at Mahendra Narayan Nidhi Institute, Gothatar, Kathmandu, Nepal was asked how she teaches language. She said that language teaching is not always done by showing films and that films are used when teaching other subjects.

When asking a teacher residing in Kalanki, Kathmandu, Nepal how do you do language teaching activities there? She said that she had to teach by showing videos of related lessons and making slides.

In a phone conversation with Preksha Bhattarai, a teacher at the International School in Ghorai, Dang, Lumbini, Nepal, said that she teaches different aspects of the language by putting on CDs of related lessons rather than what activities you do during language teaching, and divide the students into groups to note down the content related to the four language skills: listening, speaking, reading, and writing.

4.5. Focus Group Discussion (FGD)

In the presence of teachers, students at Nandi Secondary School, Kathmandu, Nepal and the academicians of other sectors, a discussion program had been conducted to explore the importance of the use of movies in language teaching. Most of the participants expressed their views that the knowledge gained from the use of movies in Nepali language teaching remains for a long time rather than other types of teaching methods. It is a student-centered teaching method; therefore, it concentrates the attention of the students on subject matter. Some of the participants, especially students, who did not have access to smartphones or smart television, were a bit confused about getting access to related content.

4.6. Analysis

In the context of Nepal, after the publication of Gorkhapatra (1952), Nepali language teaching started from B.S. 1958. With the establishment of the Gorkha Bhasha Prakashini Samiti in 1969, the organization published several textbooks for language schools. After Calcutta University recognized Nepali language as

an optional subject in B.S. 1997, Nepali teaching was started as a co-curricular subject in Darbar High School in association with the same university. After the establishment of Nepal SLC Board in 1990, Nepali language teaching takes a new turn.

Similarly, In the year B. S. 2004, Nepali teaching at primary, lower secondary and secondary level is arranged by creating a curriculum with the new concept of Aadhaar education. After the establishment of the Normal School in 2009, teachers who teach Nepali are provided with necessary training on new methods in language teaching. The creation of a primary, lower secondary language curriculum in 2016 is considered an important effort for Nepali language teaching. In this regard, after the implementation of 'National Education System Plan' in B.S. 2028, a new chapter and an epoch-making change in the Nepali teaching tradition begins. One-year M. Ed. and one-year B. Ed. Education program begins in B.S. 2029. After the start of the program, teaching training is provided to the graduates and postgraduates in various subjects. With the development of such a tradition, now Nepali education is now not only limited to postgraduate level but has also spread widely to research level. Therefore, efforts to reform and configuration of this tradition of Nepali teaching are not only limited to the country but also spread in foreign universities.

From the second year (B.S. 2028) of the fourth periodic plan of Nepal, the "Communication Plan" has been implemented. Under this plan, organizational and physical improvements related to film screening have been made to develop both audio and visual aspects, radio broadcasting, printing, recording. In addition to the textbooks, the Audio-Visual Materials easily enables students to achieve the objectives according to the curriculum. The use of these materials will not be limited to formal educational institutions but will also be included in Proud Shiksha (Elder Age) literacy programs.

According to the report of the National Education Committee, 2018, 'to influence the social education in the people of the villages, it seems necessary to have a Movie-Van in every place and show films on different subjects.

The statements of the literature review, the messages of the FDG and the theme of the previous paragraphs of this section are in the same line and suggest the use of movie (audio-video) in Nepali Language teaching.

5. FINDINGS

- ✓ Knowledge obtained from the teaching language through movies is long-lasting.
- ✓ The teaching process will be student-centered, so the students will remain disciplined and persistent.
- ✓ Film teaching will help to improve the important skills such as listening, speaking, reading, and writing as well as in adaptation of languages.

6. CONCLUSION

It seems insignificant that the educational work of the country has been done systematically using educational films. But in developed countries, films are used as an important material to organize teaching activities. Movies have a great contribution in the development and promotion of the English language. In this background, various developed countries have been using films to introduce their language, art, culture, lifestyle, religion, and historical, political and social themes to the world and because of this, their linguistic educational level is advanced. But in a less developed country like us, its use seems to be insignificant.

Due to the use and application of movies in the teaching work, students can give linguistic expression while following the grammatical rules, to understand the customs and culture of their country. Film is an audio-visual subject/genre through which students can hear and learn new information and new knowledge and skills. Knowledge that cannot be obtained by reading many books or texts can be gained by watching a few movies. Good human qualities like respect, honor and discipline can be acquired through movies. Film is such an effective medium, using which language expression can be intensified and due to its use, the basic expression skills of students such as listening, speaking, reading, and writing will be greatly changed.

People of all age groups benefit from film teaching as it teaches students more content in less time in an entertaining manner. In the current perspective, any form of film can be used to present any topic clearly. Therefore, students have been taught through this medium in Nepal since the past. In the future, it is inevitable to be able to teach in a way that remains in the minds of students through movies. When the medium of film can be used in learning, it can be taught in a learner-friendly environment. In the era of changing science and technology, teaching activities with the help of movies will be sustainable and

effective. Similarly, the teaching of this nature is meaningful and effective in performance presentations such as dialogues, metaphors, discussions etc. It also has an important place in new words and terminology.

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